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April 1-3 2025

Presentation/Poster Proposal
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Presentation Title:	Testing and characterization of AI model in STT and TTS for phone applications
Intended Audience:	

IMPORTANT: Presentations must not include any (live) tool demos (in particular not commercial tools), i.e., novel ideas must always be presented outside of a concrete tool context! Screen shots can be used to illustrate the application of the topic in a particular tool context. Structure your ideas and presentation for a 15 min presentation + 5 min questions!

**I. Summary of conference/poster presentation [max 1000 chars (with spaces) per box]
Please cover all the questions in each answer box!**

- What is the problem you are addressing and why is it important?
- How is your presentation/poster related to industrial application of automated testing?
- How is your presentation/poster related to the Call for Proposals?

Digital transformation requires to collect, analyse and use several data sources from a company's processes and workflows; one of the most common and ubiquitous sources of data is the voice, either from phone or conference calls, recorded events, etc. Most of those data are not really used, while they represent an important source of knowledge for a company and leveraging such data might give a company a competitive edge. Modern AI tools allow to convert voice stream into text (STT) and the other way round (TTS) quite easily but using those tools with phone quality audio or with languages other than English might result in unpredictable results. To support our dev team in evaluating and selecting the best algorithms for the task at hand, we are designing a testbed to automate the test of several TTS and STT algorithms in the context of the Italian language also considering several network impairments that phone media might be subject to. The testbed could be used to evaluate other languages as well, given the related data sets.

- What is the novelty in your presentation/poster?
- What technologies, tools and practices have you applied?

Several statistics and benchmarks are currently available for the English language, to compare streaming and batch algorithms and models for STT and TTS. Our search for similar data applied to other languages have fall short so far (at least for Italian language) We are interested in measuring the word error rate, accuracy, speed and latency among other parameters To do so we are taking advantage of the virtual audio devices available on GNU/Linux systems to build a media stream pipeline that will be able to automatically process audio streams of arbitrary length to calculate the parameters of interest. The SST and TTS models connectors will be "plugins" for the pipeline

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The pipeline includes tools to generate configurable network impairments and will be orchestrated using ansible.

- What are the outcomes from your solution and the lessons learnt?
- How can the approach or method be re-used by other organizations?

At the moment the project is in an early stage, but our goal is to complete the work by the end of 2024, so we expect to be able to present the pipeline architecture and the measurement results at UCAAT 2025

II. Please mark with bold the answer which categorizes best your presentation!

1. Presentation kind

- Position statement
- Experience report from practice, lessons learnt**
- Report from a larger project or activity of substantial size
- Research report, survey
- Other (please specify)

2. Level of understanding of the topic

- Beginner**
- Advanced
- Expert

3. Which stage of adoption do the results presented in this proposal reflect?

- Research prototype (results produced by research group with links to industry)

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- b. Pilot (results by a team as part of an evaluation)**
- c. Initial deployment (results in use for < 1 year in production testing)
- d. Deployment (result in use since 1+ years in production testing)

4. Main application area(s) covered in the presentation

- a. Information & Communication Technologies (ICT)**
- b. Industrial automation
- c. Transportation (Automotive, Railway, Aerospace)
- d. Enterprise IT systems**
- e. Healthcare
- f. Broadcasting
- g. Other (please specify)

III. Short bio of the author(s) [maximum 300 characters per author (with spaces)]

Annapia Rinaldi began her professional career in healthcare sector but driven by passion for technology, she obtained an ITS qualification as full stack developer. She joined NetResults S.r.l. in 2024, where she is involved in the development and integration of AI-based solution.

Paolo Labruna is a software developer with expertise in AI and natural language processing. He currently works at NetResults, developing advanced software solutions. Previously, he worked in automation software, gaining experience in optimizing processes.

Sergio Borghese graduated in Electronic Engineering at University of Pisa (Italy). He worked as a software developer in several companies ranging from user applications to device drivers. He joined NetResults S.r.l. in 2011 as the product manager and technical leader of NetResults' testing platform.